

Eviota vader, a new western Pacific dwarfgoby from Papua New Guinea (Teleostei: Gobiidae)

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Abstract

A new species of dwarfgoby, *Eviota vader*, is described from McLaren Fjord, Tufi, Papua New Guinea. The new species is characterized by a distinctive purplish-black coloration not found on any other species of dwarfgoby. In addition to the unusual color, it is diagnosed by the combination of a complete cephalic sensory-canal pore system, a dorsal/anal fin-formula of 8/7, some branched pectoral-fin rays, the fifth pelvic-fin ray present, and no dark occipital spots or any dark spots at the base of dorsal or caudal fins. The species is apparently endemic to the Tufi region of Papua New Guinea, a location known to have microendemic species.

Key words: taxonomy, ichthyology, coral-reef fishes, gobies, new species, microendemic, Tufi, black dwarfgoby

Citation: Greenfield D.W., Erdmann, M.V. & Ishida, N.K. (2025) *Eviota vader*, a new western Pacific dwarfgoby from Papua New Guinea (Teleostei: Gobiidae). *Journal of the Ocean Science Foundation*, 43, 39–44.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15786577>

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:7BC8112F-F364-4664-A9AD-B31444B209AF

Date of publication of this version of record: 3 July 2025

Introduction

The dwarfgobies in the genus *Eviota* are tiny coral-reef fishes (usually <18 mm SL) occurring throughout the Indo-Pacific Ocean. They can be relatively abundant on coral reefs, although their small size makes them difficult to observe (Greenfield 2017). There are currently 134 valid described species of dwarfgobies with a wide variety of color patterns, but none of them feature an overall dark purplish-black appearance. During a recent survey of reef fish biodiversity in the unique volcanic fjord region of Tufi in Oro Province, Papua New Guinea, the authors MVE and NKI encountered a conspicuous dark purple-colored dwarfgoby perched on a section of dead coral on a large *Porites* coral colony. The specimen was photographed underwater and subsequently collected with clove oil. Examination of the specimen by the first author confirmed this to be an undescribed species. Unfortunately, no additional specimens were encountered on the expedition. Nevertheless, its distinctive combination of color and morphological characters, present in the mature male specimen, leads us to confidently describe it as a new species.

Recent developments in underwater macrophotography, along with divers specifically searching for dwarfgobies, have resulted in a rapid increase of described species. The pioneering early researchers on the genus were Ernest Lachner and Susan Jewett (née Karnella), who, in their final collaboration (Jewett & Lachner 1983), recognized 40 species. When Greenfield & Winterbottom (2016) published their comprehensive key to the species of *Eviota*, there were 107 valid species. Subsequently, Greenfield (2021) published an addendum to the 2016 key recognizing 123 valid species. Four years later, the new species *Eviota samota* Greenfield, Erdmann & Putra, 2025 was described from Indonesia as the 134th species. This description of our new species from Papua New Guinea makes it the 135th.

Materials and Methods

The single male holotype of the new species is deposited at the California Academy of Sciences, San Francisco, CA, USA (CAS).

Descriptions of pelvic-fin morphology and cephalic sensory-canal pores follow Greenfield & Winterbottom (2016), as originally formulated by Lachner & Karnella (1980) and Jewett & Lachner (1983). We follow Lachner & Karnella (1980: 4) in describing the membranes joining the first 4 pelvic-fin rays, which “...are considered to be well developed when the membranes extend beyond the bases of the first branches; they are considered to be reduced when they are slightly developed, not extending to the bases of the first branches”. The dorsal/anal fin-ray formula count (eg. 8/8) only includes segmented rays.

Measurements were made to the nearest 0.1 mm using an ocular micrometer or dial calipers (the latter only for standard length, body depth, and caudal-peduncle depth). Lengths are given as standard length (SL), measured from the median anterior point of the upper lip to the base of the caudal fin (i.e. the posterior end of the hypural plate); the origin of the first dorsal fin is measured from the median anterior point of the upper lip to the anterior base of the first dorsal-fin spine; the origin of the second dorsal fin is measured from the median anterior point of the upper lip to the anterior base of its spine; the origin of the anal fin is measured from the median anterior point of the upper lip to the anterior base of its spine; body depth is measured at the center of the first dorsal fin; head length is taken from the upper lip to the posterior end of the opercular membrane; orbit diameter is the greatest fleshy diameter; snout length is measured from the median anterior point of the upper lip to the nearest fleshy edge of the orbit; upper jaw length is the straight-line distance from the anterior tip of the premaxilla to the end of the upper margin of the dentary where the maxilla joins behind it; caudal-peduncle depth is the least depth, and caudal-peduncle length is the horizontal distance between the verticals at the rear base of the anal fin and the caudal-fin base; pelvic-fin length is measured from the base of the pelvic-fin spine to the tip of the longest pelvic-fin soft ray.

Cyanine Blue 5R (acid blue 113) stain was used to make pores and scale outlines more obvious (Akihito et al. 1993, 2002, Saruwatari et al. 1997).

Figure 1. *Eviota vader*, fresh holotype, CAS 249349, 11.5 mm SL, male, anesthetized and underwater, Tufi, Papua New Guinea (photo reversed) (M.V. Erdmann).

Eviota vader, n. sp.

Black Dwarfgoby

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Figures 1 & 2

Holotype. CAS 249349, 11.5 mm SL male, Papua New Guinea, Tufi, McLaren Fjord, -9.06187°, 149.32303°, 4 m, field number MVE-25-008, M.V. Erdmann & N.K. Ichida, 7 March 2025.

Diagnosis. A species of *Eviota* distinguished from all congeners by a combination of a complete cephalic sensory-canal pore system (pattern 1), a dorsal/anal fin-ray formula 8/7, some pectoral-fin rays branched, fifth pelvic-fin ray present, no dark occipital spots or any dark spots at the base of dorsal or caudal fins, and a broad and fringed male urogenital papilla. Entire body and fins purplish black.

Description. Dorsal-fin elements VI+I,8, first dorsal fin triangular; spines not filamentous, last ray branched to base; anal-fin elements I,7, last ray branched to base; pectoral-fin rays 17, rays 11 through 15 branched, fin pointed, reaching to fourth anal-fin ray; pelvic-fin elements I,4, fifth ray about 10% of fourth, fourth with 3 branches; pelvic-fin membrane reduced, basal membrane reduced; 11 branched and 17 segmented caudal-fin rays; 24 lateral scales, 7 transverse scales; urogenital papilla of male broad, fringed on end; front of head rounded with an angle of about 55° from horizontal axis; mouth slanted obliquely upwards, forming an angle of about 65° to horizontal axis of body, lower jaw not projecting, maxilla extending posteriorly to center of pupil; anterior tubular nares moderate, extending just past edge of upper lip; gill opening extending forward to below posteroventral edge of preoperculum. Cephalic sensory-canal pore system complete.

Color in life. (Fig. 1) Background color of body black with purple tinges, head with more purple tinges than body. Scales running down lateral line slightly lighter, scales on ventral margin of caudal peduncle dark-cream colored. Abdomen translucent purplish grey with diffuse red/orange showing through. Top of head and nape purple with a diffuse red/orange spot just above pectoral-fin base (due to scale loss); side of head light purple with scattered small red/orange spots continuing ventrally onto gill membranes, forward onto jaws, and under eye. Pupil of eye surrounded by a yellow ring with red specks, iris purple with reddish tinge. Pectoral-fin base light purple with a diffuse orange area at base continuing onto adjacent gill membranes. Anal fin all black; caudal-fin

Figure 2. *Eviota vader*, preserved holotype, CAS 249349, 11.5 mm SL, male, Tufi, Papua New Guinea (D.W. Greenfield).

membranes black with small white and black spots running along rays; second dorsal-fin membranes black on lower half, beneath a diffuse lighter purple area becoming black distally; basal half of first dorsal fin black with small light purple spots on first 4 spines, distal half crossed by a light purple band with a black distal margin; pelvic and pectoral fins light purple.

Color in preservative. (Fig. 2) Background color of head and body light yellow, body peppered with small melanophores; pectoral-fin base with scattered small melanophores; top of head with two dark-brown blotches behind the eyes, one directly behind and one above preoperculum; in photograph, pale spot in front of first dorsal fin due to loss of scales; side of head with scattered diffuse groups of melanophores; snout and front of jaws dark brown; Basal half of first dorsal fin dark brown to black with clear areas on first 4 spines, clear area crossing above lower half, distal margin black; anal fin and second dorsal fin dark brown to black; pectoral and pelvic fins with melanophores along rays; caudal fin with rows of black spots along rays.

Etymology. The specific epithet is derived from the fictional dark figure Darth Vader in the Star Wars movie franchise (Fig. 3), referring to the fact that it is the darkest of all described dwarfgobies. It is treated as a noun in apposition.

Distribution and habitat. The new species is known only from the volcanic fjord area of Tufi, Papua New Guinea, specifically within McLaren Fjord. The single specimen was collected from 4 m depth on the reef crest, from a small burrow in the top of a large *Porites* coral bommie. The reef crest in this area was comprised of many large *Porites* and other massive corals, transitioning into branching and foliose corals occupying the reef slope at a 45° angle to a maximum depth of 40–50 m. Whereas it is likely this species is distributed more broadly in PNG, the Tufi fjord region does represent a unique habitat which is home to other microendemic fishes, such as *Chrysiptera niger* (Allen, 1975); further exploration is needed to determine the true range of this species.

Figure 3. Darth Vader, Star Wars/Ron Riccio-www.flickr.com/photos/starwarsblog/793008715/ (CC-BY-2.0).

Comparisons. There are only three species of *Eviota* with branched pectoral-fin rays that share a dorsal/anal fin-formula of 8/7 and a complete cephalic sensory-canal pore system with the new species: *Eviota pardalota* (Fig. 4A), *Eviota sodwanaensis* (Fig. 4B), and *Eviota rubriguttata* (Fig. 4C). The first two of these species are distinguished from *E. vader* by possessing two dark spots on the pectoral-fin base in *E. pardalota* and a dark occipital spot in *E. sodwanaensis*. *Eviota rubriguttata* lacks a fifth pelvic-fin ray, which is present in *E. vader*. In addition, both *E. sodwanaensis* and *E. rubriguttata* have dark spots on the caudal peduncle (not present in *E. vader*), and *E. pardalota* has a series of 8 dark spots running along the bases of the dorsal fins (vs. none in *E. vader*). The overall dark purplish-black coloration of *E. vader* in life is unlike any other described species of *Eviota*. In the key to *Eviota* species (Greenfield & Winterbottom 2016, Greenfield 2021), the new species would end at 33a, *E. rubriguttata*, but diverges in having a fifth pelvic-fin ray and dark purplish-black coloration.

Figure 4. (A) *Eviota pardalota*, Red Sea, Saudi Arabia (S. Bogorodsky); (B) *Eviota sodawanaensis*, South Africa (R. Winterbottom); (C) *Eviota rubriguttata*, Japan (T. Suzuki).

Acknowledgments

We thank Dr. Osborne Sanida, Nou Korema, and Georgia Kaipu of the Papua New Guinea National Research Institute for facilitating our research visas and for liaising with other national institutions and technical review committees to effect approval of the project. Sincere thanks are also due to Mr. Hayson Kassap of the Oro Provincial Administration and Mr. Vagi Rei, Marzena Anne Marinjembi, Juda Nundima, and Mary Palik of the PNG Conservation and Environmental Protection Agency (CEPA) for supporting this research and issuing Permit #023058 (W3 Permit to Export Wildlife). We also extend our appreciation to Jordan Honey, Luth Morales, Loni, and the highly capable dive crew of Tufi Resort for all their efforts to support our diving and expedition logistics, and we thank Matt Brooks for sponsoring the expedition and for his able assistance in the collection of fish specimens. We also thank Jess Blakeway and Christine Dudgeon from the University of the Sunshine Coast, Julie-Anne Waranaka of the University of PNG, Max Teliwa of the National Fisheries Authority, and Gerry Allen of the Western Australian Museum for their assistance in arranging the expedition and permits and for executing a successful expedition. We thank Jon Fong and Mysi Hoang of the California Academy of Sciences for providing valuable curatorial and logistic support. Finally, we thank the warm and friendly people and government of Tufi (Oro Province) for welcoming us to their beautiful area and allowing this research. The manuscript was reviewed by two reviewers.

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